

EFFECTIVE METHODS AND MEANS OF PROTECTION OF COTTON FROM AUSTROGALLIA ZACHVATKINI Vilb. IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The most effective methods of protection are described and the results of long-term observations of the dynamics of the number and harmfulness of *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. on industrial cotton crops in Fergana Valley conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan are presented. A reliable positive correlation was established between damage and the number of larvae and adults of *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. in crops. The methods and principles for selecting essential factors in developing mathematical models for forecasting the development and spread of *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb., as well as issues of territories zoning according to their weather and environmental characteristics were presented.*

Keywords: *mathematical models, essential factors, zoning of territories, forecasting, *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb., abundance, cotton.*

INTRODUCTION.

In recent years, the distribution area of some dangerous pests has been expanding year after year in the Republic of Uzbekistan: various types of aphids, whiteflies, bugs, cicadas, and, in pastures, harmful locusts [1].

Morphological and biological features of development, area of distribution, harmfulness, scientifically based forecasting and optimal timing of protective measures against the above-mentioned harmful organisms in the conditions of the republic are constantly being studied. The system of effective and environmentally safe measures for the protection of certain agricultural crops has not yet been sufficiently developed.

Despite the successful fight against harmful organisms of cotton, many problems of organizing the monitoring of harmful organisms on the territory of the republic, the development of scientifically based forecasts of the emergence, development and spread of especially dangerous species, the introduction of modern methods of monitoring harmful organisms remain unresolved.

Based on the above, the purpose of this article is to develop systems for protecting cotton from *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb, which is one of the economically dangerous species of insects that require monitoring of the populations state due to its high numbers, harmfulness, and wide distribution.

RESULTS.

Among the least studied insects in Uzbekistan are cicadas, although they are serious pests of cultivated plants, losses from which can reach up to 15-17%, and carriers of many dangerous viral diseases.

At present, it cannot yet be said that even the species composition of these insects in our Republic has been identified to a sufficiently complete degree.

Evidence of this is the fact that new for science species and even new genera of this group of insects, which are true pests of agricultural plants, are still being discovered and described [2].

Austroagallia zachvatkini Vilb., differs well from the most harmful *Empoasca meridiana* Zachv., *Kyboasca bipunctata* Osh. in habitus, proportions and body color.

Austroagallia zachvatkini Vilb. is larger than the previous two species. The male size is 3.4-3.8 mm, the female size is 3.7-3.9 mm. According to morphological characteristics, it is easily distinguished from other species by its light color, four black round spots, two of which are located on the crown, and the other two at the posterior edge of the pronotum opposite the first two.

In autumn, in October or in the first half of November, *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. disappears from the fields and henceforth adult individuals are not found in the fields. Collections show that no adults of this species were found during the wintering period.

The imago *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. is not only absent in soil samples, it was also not found during inspection of various areas adjacent to cotton fields. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. overwinters in the egg phase.

In spring, adults appear in cotton fields relatively late. However, the larvae of *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. appear in early April or late March. It depends on the meteorological conditions in spring.

The development of larvae continues for 45-50 days and ends in the first half of May.

According to the author A.G. Kozhevnikova, the larvae in the conditions of the Tashkent region are distinguished by the following morphological characteristics. They are squat, brownish with yellow spots and a longitudinal yellow blurry stripe along the top. Their body is bumpy, covered with rather long light hairs.

Future females are of course similar to future males, but they are larger in size. It can be noted that at the fifth instar, the larvae of *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. already differ by sex. In male larvae, the genital sclerites are well developed, and in future females, the pygophore and longitudinal strip of the ovipositor [3].

The emergence of wings of first generation larvae is prolonged; in the first generation imagoes wings emerge from the end of April to mid-May. After a short feeding period, the adults mate and begin laying eggs.

The second generation larvae appear at the beginning of the first decade of June. In Kibray district of Tashkent region they hatch from the middle of the first decade of June to the middle of the second decade of July. Their development continues for about 40 days.

Larvae of the third generation hatch in the first decade of August and are found until the middle of the second decade of September.

Austroagallia zachvatkini Vilb. die out in mid-November.

The number of *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. gradually increases towards the end of the season.

When the food plant becomes coarse, the cicada moves on to other vegetative plants.

Some regions of the republic (Tashkent, Andijan, Namangan, Fergana) are in the zone of constant high numbers and significant harmfulness of cicadas (*Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb.). This is due to the instability of the phytosanitary situation, which provokes periodic outbreaks of pests mass reproduction.

The cyclicity of mass reproduction of *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. reveals a connection with changes in solar activity, climatic conditions and anthropogenic impacts [1-3]. In this regard, in order to predict crop losses from *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. and plan scientifically based plant protection measures, it is necessary to conduct phytosanitary monitoring in a timely manner, allowing to assess the number and state of this species population, which requires the availability of simple, effective and accessible methods for predicting the timing of appearance, accounting for the number and harmfulness of *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb.

When developing mathematical models for predicting the development of harmful cicadas, including *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb., when selecting significant factors, it is advisable to use the method for determining the information weight of features given in [4-6, 8-10].

The task of optimized zoning of agricultural territories according to weather and environmental characteristics are necessary links in the scientific understanding of the continuously changing environment. Work in this area is of great practical importance, since zoning acts as an essential element in many studies, in particular in forecasting the number of cicadas, the size of areas infested by pests, the date of pests' appearance, planning pest control measures, in analyzing the causes of pests' outbreaks, etc. [9].

Zoning according to reproduction characteristics and timing of the main phenological phases of harmful organisms allows us to identify zones with different pest reproduction rates.

To solve problems of zoning in plant protection, a class of pattern recognition algorithms is used [6, 7 - 10]. The problem of spontaneous division of a set of objects is solved using algorithms for calculating estimates using some quantitative measures characterizing the information content of both the features and the objects themselves.

The division of objects into classes in this case is based on the assumption that when ordered by the value of the latter, objects will be grouped by rank. The division obtained in this way is an intermediate stage of spontaneous classification. The final division is obtained only after the object's belonging to its class is confirmed by voting.

Therefore, by allocating areas into corresponding classes, it is possible to apply the results of forecasting the timing of cicadas' appearance, including *Austroagallia zachvatkini* Vilb. and to organize protective measures against them in other areas belonging to the same class.

Findings and conclusions. The system of controlling harmful organisms of agricultural crops, practiced in the past decades, mainly through the massive use of chemicals, especially when their use was not sufficiently justified in ecological and economic terms, led to the emergence of serious problems associated with the negative impact on the environment and the emergence of resistance of harmful organisms to plant protection means. In part, this even contributed to a direct or indirect increase in the harmfulness of certain types of pests and diseases and the effectiveness of measures to control them. In this regard, in recent years, biological and microbiological methods of controlling agricultural pests have become increasingly widespread as they best meet the principles of environmental protection.

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